

WHEN ACADEMIC WORDS START TO WORK: INTEGRATING AUTHENTIC TEXTS AND AUDIOVISUAL RECOURCES IN ACADEMIC VOCABULARY INSTRUCTION

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Abstract. *At advanced stages of language learning, students often demonstrate a discrepancy between receptive knowledge of academic vocabulary and its productive use. While learners may successfully recognize key lexical items in reading and listening, their ability to apply such vocabulary in speaking and writing remains limited. This article explores the pedagogical potential of integrating authentic texts and audiovisual resources in teaching academic English vocabulary, with particular attention to underlying neurocognitive mechanisms. The study is based on classroom observations involving C1-level learners and examines how multimodal input—combining textual, visual, and auditory channels—supports deeper processing and retention. Drawing on theoretical perspectives from applied linguistics and cognitive psychology, including dual coding theory and associative memory, the paper argues that academic vocabulary is more effectively acquired when encountered in varied, meaningful contexts. The findings suggest that the integrations of authentic and audiovisual materials contribute to improved lexical usage, increased learner confidence, and more flexible language production. The role of digital technologies in facilitating access to such materials is also discussed.*

Keywords: *academic vocabulary, authentic materials, audiovisual resources, neurocognitive learning, digital pedagogy*

Ключевые слова: *академическая лексика, аутентичные материалы, аудиовизуальные ресурсы, нейрокогнитивное обучение, цифровая педагогика*

Kalit so‘zlar: *akademik leksika, autentik materiallar, audiovisual resurslar, neyrokognitiv o‘rganish, raqamli ta’lim.*

INTRODUCTION. At advanced levels of English proficiency, learners often reach a point where communicative fluency is no longer sufficient. While everyday interaction becomes relatively effortless, difficulties emerge in more formal and academic contexts. Students may understand complex texts and follow lectures with little difficulty, yet struggle to express ideas with precision, coherence, and appropriate lexical choice.

This discrepancy between recognition and production is particularly evident in relation to academic vocabulary. Learners frequently recognize terms such as “significant”, “approach”, or “assumption”, but hesitate to use them independently. As argued by Nation (2001), vocabulary knowledge extends beyond meaning and includes aspects such as collocation, grammatical behavior, and contextual appropriateness.

This persistence of this gap raises questions about instructional practices. Academic vocabulary is often taught through decontextualized methods, including word lists and definitions, which may support short-term retention but do not necessarily lead to active use. In contrast, authentic texts and audiovisual resources offer opportunities for contextualized exposure. The

present study examines how such materials, supported by neurocognitive principles, may contribute to more effective academic vocabulary acquisition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instructional Materials: Authentic Texts and Audiovisual Resources

The instructional approach was based on the integration of authentic academic texts and audiovisual materials. Authentic texts included short academic articles, adapted research summaries, and argumentative essays reflecting real academic discourse. These materials were selected for their relevance, clarity, and lexical richness.

Audiovisual resources consisted primarily of recorded lectures, educational video content, and academic presentations available through digital platforms. Such materials provided not only linguistic input but also visual support in the form of slides, diagrams, and graphical representations.

As noted by Mayer (2009), the combination of verbal and visual input enhances comprehension and retention.

In the context of academic vocabulary, audiovisual materials allow learners to observe how lexical items function within spoken discourse, supported by intonation, emphasis, and visual context.

Theoretical Framework: Neurocognitive Principles of Vocabulary Acquisition

The study draws on several key concepts from cognitive psychology. Dual coding theory, proposed by Paivio (1986) and further developed by Mayer (2009), suggests that information encoded through both verbal and visual channels is more likely to be retained.

Associative memory, as described by Baddeley (1997), plays a central role in vocabulary acquisition. Words learned in context become linked to surrounding information, creating multiple pathways for retrieval. For example, an academic term encountered in a lecture may be associated with a specific example or visual representation.

Cognitive load theory also informs the approach. Academic language often places significant demands on working memory. Audiovisual input helps distribute this load by providing additional cues, thereby facilitating comprehension.

Repetition remains essential, but its effectiveness depends on variation. As argued by Nation (2001), repeated exposure across different contexts supports long-term retention more effectively than isolated repetition.

Participants and Instructional Context

The study was conducted with a group of C1-level learners enrolled in an advanced English course. The participants demonstrated strong receptive skills in reading and listening but experienced difficulties in the productive use of academic vocabulary.

Instruction was organized over several sessions, during which authentic texts and audiovisual materials were systematically integrated into classroom activities. The focus was on encouraging active engagement with academic vocabulary through contextualized tasks.

Instructional Procedures

The instructional process involved a sequence of activities designed to reinforce vocabulary through multiple modalities.

One approach combined reading and viewing tasks. Students were first introduced to a short academic text containing target vocabulary. This was followed by a related video lecture, allowing learners to encounter the same lexical items in a different context.

Reformulation tasks were also used. Students were asked to transform informal instructions into more academic equivalents. For example, “This is very important”

was reformulated as “This is highly significant”. Such activities encouraged active use of vocabulary rather than passive recognition.

In addition, discussion tasks required students to incorporate target vocabulary into spoken responses. These tasks were initially challenging but gradually led to more confident usage.

Digital tools supported the learning process by enabling repeated exposure. Features such as subtitles, playback control, and annotation allowed students to revisit materials as needed.

RESULTS

The integration of authentic texts and audiovisual materials resulted in observable changes in students’ use of academic vocabulary. Learners demonstrated increased willingness to incorporate target lexical items into both speaking and writing tasks.

Vocabulary encountered across multiple modalities was recalled more frequently and used with greater contextual accuracy. In particular, students showed improved ability to use words such as “significant”, “indicate”, and “approach” in appropriate context.

Although the data is based primarily on classroom observation rather than quantitative measurement, the consistency of these patterns suggests a positive impact of the instructional approach. Students also reported greater confidence in using academic vocabulary, particularly after repeated exposure through video and text.

DISCUSSION

The findings appear to support the view that academic vocabulary is more effectively acquired through contextualized and multimodal input.

From a neurocognitive perspective, this can be explained by the interaction of dual coding, associative memory, and contextual repetition.

The use of audiovisual materials provides additional channels for processing information, reducing cognitive load and facilitating comprehension. At the same time, authentic texts expose learners to natural patterns of language use, supporting the development of lexical competence.

Digital technologies play an important role in this process by increasing access to authentic materials and enabling flexible interaction with content. As noted by Polat (2009), the integration of technology in education enhances both engagement and effectiveness.

However, the success of this approach depends on careful selection and structuring of materials. Without appropriate guidance, authentic input may become overwhelming. Therefore, the role of the teacher remains central.

CONCLUSION

The teaching of academic vocabulary remains a complex task, particularly at advanced levels. Traditional methods, while useful, may not fully address the challenges associated with productive use.

The integration of authentic texts and audiovisual resources offers a promising alternative. By providing contextualized and multimodal input, this approach aligns with fundamental principles of memory and learning.

The findings suggest that academic vocabulary is more effectively acquired when it is experienced in varied contexts rather than memorized in isolation. When supported by digital technologies and appropriate pedagogical strategies, authentic materials can facilitate the transition from passive recognition to active use.

REFERENCES

1. Nation, I. S. P. (2001). *Learning Vocabulary in Another Language*. Cambridge University Press.
2. Schmitt, N. (2000). *Vocabulary in Language Teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
3. Mayer, R. E. (2009). *Multimedia Learning*. Cambridge University Press.
4. Paivio, A. (1986). *Mental Representations*. Oxford University Press.
5. Gilmore, A. (2007). *Authentic materials in language teaching*. *Language Teaching*.
6. Baddeley, A. (1997). *Human Memory*. Psychology Press.
7. Полат, Е. С. (2009). *Современные педагогические технологии*. Москва.
8. Сафонова, В.В. (2016). *Межкультурная коммуникация*. Москва.
9. Хамраев, М. (2015). *Лингвистический анализ*. Ташкент.
10. Рахматуллаев, Ш. (2006). *Узбекский язык*. Ташкент.